

CERAMOR-MAP, UTRA-LIGHT ADVANCED CERAMIC ARMOR SYSTEM FOR PERSONAL AND VEHICLE PROTECTION

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Summary

Aceram Technologies have completed an R&D program on the development of a new advanced ceramic armor system – CERAMOR-MAP[®] (CERAMic arMOR Modular Advanced Protection). The new system has been designed specifically for improved personal protection, but has been expanded and modified for use as add-on armor on aircraft and vehicles as well. The CERAMOR-MAP armor systems are exclusively commercialized and produced by CERAMOR Defence, located in Watertown, New York, USA.

This paper describes briefly the system consisting of a spall cover, CERAMOR ceramic components, shock absorber, backing and for vehicle the steel hull with or without internal liner. The advancements reside in materials selection including the CERAMOR ceramic composite, the system components and their design for performing desired functions in the complex system. The new armor system is based on a tougher ceramic composite material (CERAMOR[®]) that provides closer than ever multi-hit capability, and a novel design approach to the ceramic components as well as the entire system. The advances in design are based on a dual role played by the ceramic: deflecting and defeating the threats. The role designed for each component of the system is outlined and exemplified.

Ballistic test results for high-level threats are also presented and discussed on personal protection Level IV Special CERAMOR-MAP[®] strike plates and STANAG level 4 vehicle protection. In conclusions, the improved ballistic performance of the new Advanced Ceramic Armor System is outlined.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic armor systems have gained acceptance as lightweight ballistic protection for the personnel and assets. Generally, ceramic systems comprise mainly of an engineering ceramic component on the strike side bonded to a ductile absorbing backing. The advantage of ceramic armor over more conventional armor resides in the high hardness and relatively low density of the ceramic material.

However, what the ceramic provides to the armor system by the way of resistance to penetration and low weight is normally countered by the low fracture toughness of the material [1], and consequently ceramics are brittle and shatter under the impact, resulting in a limited multi-hit capabilities for the armor. The detrimental effect of fracture toughness on ballistic performance was emphasized through the rod penetration experiments conducted to understand the failure mechanism [2].

Armor systems shall offer protection against high level threats and consequently, system's design and architecture has to focus on defeating the projectiles, while accommodating the impact energy with reduced back face deformation. Robert Kinney [3] recently outlined the importance of armor system architecture for personal protection.

The new CERAMOR[®] ceramic armor system was introduced through engineering design improvements aimed to improve ballistic performance by deflecting the projectile and reducing the energy conoid. [4]

The ceramic material is a new functional alumina composite (CERAMOR[®]) with high fracture toughness acting also as a crack arrester. Overall, the CERAMOR system architecture [4] has been engineered and designed to provide advanced protection against high-speed armor piercing projectiles including the tungsten carbide core. CERAMOR-MAP[®] ARMOR SYSTEM

CERAMOR –MAP[®] Ceramic Component

The CERAMOR[®] material is a new functional alumina based composite designed to provide mechanical properties suitable for ballistic applications. The development work focussed on increasing the fracture toughness, while the hardness and strength of the alumina were preserved or even improved. This approach was based on the need of high fracture toughness of the ceramic outlined in the earlier work of Hazell and Iremonger [2]. The new CERAMOR[®] ceramic is a two-phase composite that exhibits a hardness of 17.2 GPa, (slightly higher than 16.4 GPa of alumina); strength of 492 MPa, (similar to alumina), and a fracture toughness of 6.9–7.2 MPa m^{1/2} about three times higher than any other ceramic materials.

The main role of the ceramic in any armor system is defeating the projectile based on the high hardness of the material. The CERAMOR new MAP design is based on creating deflective surfaces through an array of nodes (bumps) on the strike face that generates the dual role for the ceramic to deflect and defeat the projectiles. MAP design study involved nodes of different shape, sizes and distributions. Following an optimization process, ceramic chest plates and hexagonal tiles with spherical nodes of mono-modal distribution on the strike face of the ceramic were produced by slip casting and pressing respectively. The ceramic component has the dual role of defeating the projectile with concentrated damage area as the ceramic acts as crack arrester because of its high fracture toughness. Figure 1 shows a CERAMOR-MAP[®] armor panel with spherical nodes on the strike face before and after ballistic testing with 14.5 mm AP B32 projectiles at 910 m/s.

Figure 1. CERAMOR-MAP armor panel of 12"x12 with mono-modal spherical nodes distribution before and after ballistic testing with 14.5 mm projectiles.

CERAMOR[®] Armor System

The CERAMOR MAP - is an advanced, ultra-light armor system [6] for vehicle and personal protection, based on a proprietary ceramic material formulation and advancements in component and system design. The system provides enhanced advanced protection through its unique patented design features [4]. In general, the CERAMOR system comprises of:

- A polycarbonate, or polycarbonate fibre composite spall cover on the strike face of the ceramic
- Ceramic component with or without nodes
- A stiff polymer-fibre composite named “shock absorber” behind the ceramic designed to disturb the impact conoid and reduce the dynamic deformation of the backing

- Degraded hybrid commercial backing made of Kevlar[®], Twaron[®], Titan-Kevlar, Spectra-Shield[®], Titan Spectra, Dyneema, Zylon, usually a combination of the above.

The integration of these components into a bullet resistant plate and a vehicle panel is done in an autoclave and a press, respectively, under controlled temperature and pressure conditions. The system architecture is sketched in Figure 2 along with an integrated CERAMOR-MAP strike plate without cover.

Advanced CERAMOR System architecture

Figure 2. CERAMOR system architecture and the strike face of an integrated CERAMOR - MAP bullet resistant plate.

The polycarbonate spall cover, the shock absorber and the unique ceramic component design, as well as the whole system are under pending world-wide patent protection. CERAMOR- MAP provides enhanced prevention and advanced protection as a result of the technological and engineering advancements incorporated in the system architecture.

CERAMOR[®] ceramic is an alumina (Al_2O_3) based ceramic-ceramic composite with high hardness and fracture toughness that acts as a crack arrester and it is the core of the system. The advancements in the ceramic component design with nodes on the strike face provide deflection of the projectile, shock wave anti-resonance and the hexagonal geometry of the tiles allows homogeneous directional dispersion of the conoid after impact, as well as, interlocked panels on the vehicle.

Overall, the CERAMOR system has been designed for:

Enhanced Prevention in Detection of the vehicles:

Stealth for infrared detection as a result of the air gap and ceramics low thermal conductivity

Reduce radar detection as a result of the scattering by the nodes

Camouflage paint on the surface

Advanced Protection for the vehicle and personal

Ultra-light system having an areal density similar to boron carbide

Unsurpassed shot closeness (2x14.5 mm AP b32 at 2" apart)

Unique multi-hit capabilities as more than 5 shots per square foot

Easy upgrade from a level of threat to the next one

The system provides enhanced protection through their unique features:

- Ceramic properties and system design tailored for rough handling, impact resistance and high endurance
- Complete protection for a given threat design against any level of threat projectiles
- Extreme multi-hit capabilities without bridge cracking or shattering of the ceramic
- Designed specifically for tungsten carbide penetrators
- Ultra light, low areal density

The whole CERAMOR[®]-MAP system has been designed based on the dual functions concept of deflecting the armor piercing (AP) projectiles before defeating them. The projectile fragments are stopped by the shock absorber while the backing has the role to retain small ceramic fragments that cut through the shock absorber. As a result in weighting the system the emphasis is on the ceramic component, which has to perform its role for a given level of threat.

BALLISTIC PERFORMANCE OF CERAMOR SYSTEM

The CERAMOR systems have been extensively tested for various level of threat. The systems showed to be resilient with excellent ballistic performance. The CERAMOR-MAP[®] systems with an areal density of 64 Kg/m² (13 lbs/sqft) offer advanced ballistic protection and improved performance as exemplified below for STANAG Level 4 vehicle protection. Figure 3 shows a CERAMOR ballistic panel tested with 14.5 mm AP B32 projectiles at 910 m/s with shots 5 cm apart.

Figure 3. Multi-hit and shots closeness capabilities of CERAMOR-MAP system for vehicle armor versus 14.5 mm AP B32 projectiles.

Multi-hit capabilities of the CERAMOR system for personal protection were proven by ballistic tests at H.P. White Laboratories using 7.62 mm AP M2 and Bofors projectiles. Eight shots at muzzle velocity stopped by a single strike plate without any bridge cracking between the impacts. Some of the results are displayed in Figure 4. showing two CERAMOR-MAP ceramic inserts of 7.2 psf areal density with their multi-hit capabilities.

Figure 4. Multi-hit and shots closeness capabilities of CERAMOR-MAP system for personal protection versus 7.62 mm AP M2 and Bofors projectiles.

CONCLUSIONS

In summary, high level of personal ballistic protection was achieved by the CERAMOR armor system through:

- An alumina based composite with high fracture toughness; a unique proprietary ceramic material formulation tailored to improve ballistic performance with close multi-hit capabilities and reduced damaged area
- A novel design of the ceramic component with dual function of deflecting the projectile before defeating it; while reducing the shock-waves after impact;
- Light advanced composite “Shock absorber” between the ceramic and commercial backing.
- A novel spall cover of the ceramic mitigating spall

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